

Material Design of Composite Laminates with Required In-Plane Elastic Properties

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ABSTRACT

New design method of composite laminates which have required in-plane elastic properties is proposed in this paper. The materials intended for this paper are multiple balanced angle-plyed symmetric laminates with one kind of lamina.

A newly constructed diagram for lamination parameter made possible to determine the design specifications based on four in-plane effective engineering constants. The lamination parameter is a function of the angles of fiber orientation. A certain constitution of laminates is indicated as a point in the diagram in which contours of four in-plane effective engineering constants can be drawn. Using these contour lines, the design specification is easily determined as a point on this diagram. Thus, the point can be called as a design point.

It became possible to specify the fiber orientation angle of each ply using the lamination parameters indicated as the point in the diagram.

INTRODUCTION

The elastic properties and strength of fiber reinforced plastics can be changed remarkably by changing the kind of fiber and matrix, the number of plies, and fiber orientation angles. When we utilize this advantage, we can design the composite laminates with required mechanical properties.

Tsai and Hahn (1) developed a new evaluation method of mechanical properties of composite laminates. The stiffness and strength of composite laminates can be evaluated easily by using a programmable pocket calculator which have the programs for the solutions. With this method, we can choose the optimal laminates from many proposed ones.

However, it is very difficult to propose the proper laminates for a certain application. To avoid this difficulty, the author proposed a new approach for designing composite laminates. The selection of kinds of fibers and matrices and the determination of fiber orientation angles can be done directly from the imposed conditions on elastic properties of composite laminates.

IN-PLANE ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Composite Laminates Intended for This Study

The composite laminates intended for this study are multiple balanced angle-plyed symmetric laminates (MBAS laminates) which have the fiber orientation angles of $\pm\theta_r$ ($r=1,\dots,n$) and symmetric stacking sequences.

In-plane elastic properties are considered in this study. The factors affecting the in-plane elastic properties are the elastic properties of a lamina or a single ply, fiber orientation angles, and the volumetric ratios of the ply groups with same fiber orientation angles. The ratio is referred to as ply ratio hereafter. In this paper, the constitution of laminates means the fiber orientation angles and the ply ratio. Then the constitution of MBAS laminates is presented as the following code.

$$[(\pm\theta_1)_{v_1}, \dots, (\pm\theta_n)_{v_n}]_s \tag{1}$$

where v_r means the ply ratio of the ply group with the fiber orientation angles of $\pm\theta_r$, n is the number of ply groups, and the subscript s denotes the symmetric laminates. It should be noticed that this code presents only the constitution of laminates, not the stacking sequence, because the stacking sequence does not affect the in-plane elastic properties. The ply ratio v_r satisfies the following relation.

$$\sum_{r=1}^n v_r = 1 \tag{2}$$

In-Plane Elastic Properties of MBAS Laminates

The effective engineering elastic constants, that is, E_1 :in-plane longitudinal modulus, E_2 :in-plane transverse modulus, E_6 :in-plane shear modulus, and ν_1 : in-plane Poisson's ratio, are considered as in-plane elastic properties of MBAS laminates. The subscript 1 and 2 represent the major and minor principal material axes of laminates, and the subscript 6 is used to designate the shear component in 1-2 coordinate system.

The relations between the average stress $\bar{\sigma}_i$ and the constant strain ϵ_i^o of a laminate is represented as follows.

$$\bar{\sigma}_i = \sum_j A_{ij}^* \epsilon_j^o \quad (i,j=1,2,6) \tag{3}$$

Tsai and Hahn (2) gave the expression for the nomalized in-plane stiffness A_{ij}^* as follows.

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_{11}^* \\ A_{22}^* \\ A_{12}^* \\ A_{66}^* \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} U_1 & V_1^* & V_2^* \\ U_1 & -V_1^* & V_2^* \\ U_4 & 0 & -V_2^* \\ U_5 & 0 & -V_2^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \end{bmatrix} \tag{4}$$

where U_m ($m=1,2,3,4,5$) is the linear combinations of on-axis modulus of a lamina, and V^* 's are represented as follows.

$$V_1^* = \sum_{r=1}^n v_r \cos 2\theta_r, \quad V_2^* = \sum_{r=1}^n v_r \cos 4\theta_r \tag{5}$$

In this paper, V^* 's are referred to as lamination parameters. The effective engineering elastic constants are obtained from A_{ij}^* as follows.

$$E_1 = \frac{A_{11}^* A_{22}^* - A_{12}^{*2}}{A_{22}^*}, \quad E_2 = \frac{A_{11}^* A_{22}^* - A_{12}^{*2}}{A_{11}^*}, \quad E_6 = A_{66}^*, \quad \nu_1 = \frac{A_{12}^*}{A_{22}^*} \tag{6}$$

Table I shows the values of U_m of typical composites.

Table I The values of U's of typical composites (GPa)

Material	U ₁	U ₂	U ₃	U ₄	U ₅
T300/5208	76.37	85.73	19.71	22.61	26.88
Kevlar49/Epoxy	32.44	35.55	8.65	10.54	10.95
Scotchply 1002	20.47	15.40	3.33	5.53	7.47

Ref. (3)

LAMINATION PARAMETER DIAGRAM

Allowable Region of Lamination Parameters

The design of composite laminates with required in-plane elastic properties begins with the determination of the design specifications for the effective engineering elastic constants. The author propose a lamination parameter diagram to determine the possible design specifications

The diagram of the lamination parameters V_1^* (as abscissa) and V_2^* (as ordinate) is considered. The lamination parameters is determined by Eq.(5) when the constitution of a laminate is given, and then the point on the lamination parameter diagram is determined. This point is referred to as lamination point.

In order to investigate the possibility on in-plane elastic properties of composite laminate, the allowable region of lamination parameters should be clarified. From Eq.(5), the following conditions hold.

$$-1 \leq V_1^* , V_2^* \leq 1 \tag{7}$$

When the number of kind of fiber orientation angle is one, Eq.(5) is reduced to the following.

$$V_1^* = \cos 2\theta , V_2^* = \cos 4\theta \tag{8}$$

In this case, the following equation holds.

$$V_2^* = 2V_1^{*2} - 1 \tag{9}$$

Consequently, the allowable region of lamination parameters is represented by the curve ABC in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Allowable region (curve ABC) of the lamination parameters. The fiber orientation angle is $\pm\theta$.

When the number of kinds of fiber orientation angles is two, Eq.(5) is re-written as follows.

$$V_1^* = v_1 \cos 2\theta_1 + v_2 \cos 2\theta_2 , V_2^* = v_1 \cos 4\theta_1 + v_2 \cos 4\theta_2 \tag{10}$$

The necessary and sufficient conditions to obtain the orientation angles θ_1 and θ_2 are

$$-1 \leq \cos 2\theta_r \leq 1 \quad (r=1,2) \tag{11}$$

From Eqs. (10) and (11), the following inequalities can be obtained.

$$V_2^* \geq 2V_1^{*2} - 1 \tag{12}$$

where the ply ratio v_r is supposed to be varied continuously from zero to unity, that is, the total number of plies is supposed to be sufficiently large.

Figure 2 shows the allowable region of lamination parameters of MBAS laminates with two kinds of orientation angles $\pm\theta_1$ and $\pm\theta_2$.

Fig. 2 Allowable region (hatched region) of the lamination parameters. The fiber orientation angles are $\pm\theta_1$ and $\pm\theta_2$.

When the number of kinds of fiber orientation angles is n , the evaluation of $V_2^* - (2V_1^{*2} - 1)$ yields the allowable region of lamination parameters.

$$\begin{aligned} V_2^* - (2V_1^{*2} - 1) &= \sum_{r=1}^n v_r \cos 4\theta_r - 2 \left(\sum_{r=1}^n v_r \cos 2\theta_r \right)^2 - 1 \\ &= 2 \sum_{r=1}^n v_r (\cos 2\theta_r - \sum_{r=1}^n v_r \cos 2\theta_r)^2 \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

From Eq. (13), the term $V_2^* - (2V_1^{*2} - 1)$ is non-negative, and is zero only in the case that the orientation angle θ_r is the same. Therefore the allowable region of the lamination parameter is also the same region for MBAS laminates with two kinds of orientation angles.

Contours of Effective Engineering Elastic Constants on the Lamination Parameter Diagram

When the lamination parameters V_1^* and V_2^* are determined, the effective engineering elastic constants are evaluated by using Eqs. (4) and (6). The contours of longitudinal modulus E_1 can be drawn from these relations. The expression for E_1 -contour is obtained as follows.

$$V_2^* = \frac{U_2^2 V_1^{*2} - U_2 E_1 V_1^* + U_1 E_1 - U_1^2 + U_4^2}{U_3 (2U_1 + 2U_4 - E_1)} \tag{E_1-contour} \tag{14}$$

Similarly, E_2 -contour, E_6 -contour, and v_1 -contour are obtained as follows.

$$V_2^* = \frac{U_2^2 V_1^{*2} + U_2 E_2 V_1^* + U_1 E_2 - U_1^2 + U_4^2}{U_3 (2U_1 + 2U_4 - E_2)} \tag{E_2-contour} \tag{15}$$

$$V_2^* = \frac{U_5 - E_6}{U_3} \tag{E_6-contour}, \quad V_2^* = \frac{v_1 U_2 V_1^* - v_1 U_1 + U_4}{(1+v_1)U_3} \tag{v_1-contour} \tag{16} \& \tag{17}$$

The design specifications for effective engineering elastic constants can be easily determined by using the lamination parameter diagram with these contours.

Figure 3 shows the lamination parameter diagrams of typical composites. Since the E_6 -contour becomes parallel to the abscissa, the E_6 -scale instead of E_6 -contour can be drawn.

Fig.3 Lamination parameter diagrams of typical fibrous composites.

- Glass/Epoxy (Scotchply 1002) (Above left)
- Aramid/Epoxy (Kevlar49/Epoxy) (Above right)
- Graphite/Epoxy (T300/5208) (Right)

The possible combination of the effective engineering elastic constants can be investigated easily with these diagrams.

DETERMINATION OF THE CONSTITUTION OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Suppose that the following conditions are given for effective engineering elastic constants.

$$E_1 \geq 120, E_2 \geq 40, E_6 \geq 15 \text{ (GPa)}, 0.1 \leq \nu_1 \leq 0.3 \quad (18)$$

Since a region which satisfied the above conditions is obtained in the lamination parameter diagram of T300/5208, this material can be used. Figure 4 shows the region which is referred to as the feasible design region. One design point which gives the values of V_1^* and V_2^* is determined when another evaluation condition for effective engineering elastic constants is imposed. For example, the maximization of E_2 yields the design point as the point P in Fig. 4. The values of the lamination parameters V_1^* and V_2^* are obtained easily by using the V^* -scales of the diagram, or from the calculation for the intersecting point of contour lines, exactly. In this case, the values of V_1^* and V_2^* for the point P is as follows.

$$V_1^* = 0.395, V_2^* = 0.603 \quad (19)$$

Fig. 4 Feasible design region on the lamination parameter diagram. The condition of Eq. (18) is satisfied in this hatched region.

The constitution of laminates can be determined from these values.

(I) In the Case that the Number of the Kinds of Orientation Angles is Two
From Eq. (10), the orientation angles are obtained as follows.

$$\theta_1 = \frac{1}{2} \cos^{-1} T_1, \quad \theta_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cos^{-1} T_2 \quad (20)$$

where

$$T_1 = \frac{2v_1 V_1^* \pm \sqrt{[2v_1 v_2 (1 + V_2^* - 2V_1^{*2})]}}{2v_1}, \quad T_2 = \frac{V_1^* - v_1 T_1}{v_2}$$

The ply ratios v_1 and v_2 should be given appropriately in order that the condition

$$v_1 + v_2 = 1 \quad (21)$$

is satisfied and the values of v 's are multiples of $2/N$ where N is the total number of plies. When $N=20$, then the constitution of laminates is obtained as shown in Table II.

Table II Constitution of laminate (I) (In case of the orientation angles of $\pm\theta_1$ and $\pm\theta_2$)

Ply ratio v_1	Orientation θ_1 (deg.)	Orientation θ_2 (deg.)
0.3	73.35	11.57

Note: $v_2 = 1 - v_1$; Material: T300/5208

(II) In the Case that the Number of the Kinds of Orientation Angles are Three and One Orientation Angle is zero The lamination parameters is given as follows.

$$V_1^* = v_1 \cos 2\theta_1 + v_2 \cos 2\theta_2 + v_3, \quad V_2^* = v_1 \cos 4\theta_1 + v_2 \cos 4\theta_2 + v_3 \quad (22)$$

where

$$v_1 + v_2 + v_3 = 1 \quad (23)$$

The orientation angles θ_1 and θ_2 are obtained from Eq. (22).

$$\theta_1 = \frac{1}{2} \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{V_1^* - v_2^* \theta - v_3}{v_1} \right), \quad \theta_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cos^{-1} \theta \quad (24)$$

where

$$\Theta = \frac{-K_b \pm \sqrt{(K_b^2 - K_a K_c)}}{K_a}, \quad K_a = 2v_2(v_1 + v_2), \quad K_b = 2v_2(v_3 - v_1^*),$$

$$K_c = 2v_3^2 + 2(v_1 - 2v_1^*)v_3 - (1 + v_2^*)v_1 + 2v_1^{*2}$$

The values of ply ratios v_1 and v_2 should be given similarly as mentioned before. When $N=20$, then the constitutions of laminates are determined as shown in Table III. These constitutions are equivalent in respect of in-plane elastic properties.

Table III Constitutions of the laminates (II) (In the case of the orientation angles of $\pm\theta_1$, $\pm\theta_2$ and $\pm\theta_3$)

No.	Ply ratio v_1	Orientation θ_1 (deg.)	Ply ratio v_2	Orientation θ_2 (deg.)
1	0.1	35.55	0.3	71.47
2	0.2	22.78	0.3	72.72
3	0.3	73.03	0.3	18.13
4	0.3	73.17	0.4	15.52
5	0.3	73.26	0.5	13.79
6	0.3	73.31	0.6	12.53
7	0.3	73.35	0.7	11.57

Note: $\theta_3=0$, $v_3=1-v_1-v_2$, Material: T300/5208

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The designing procedure of composite laminates with required in-plane elastic properties is as follows.

- Step 1 : Give inequality constraints on effective engineering elastic constants as design specifications.
- Step 2 : Choose one among materials available by using their lamination parameter diagrams. When a feasible design region is not obtained for all materials, the constraints should be relaxed.
- Step 3 : Give a evaluation condition on effective engineering elastic constants, e.g. the maximization of E_2 . This yields a design point in the feasible design region.
- Step 4 : The ply ratios and the fiber orientation angles are determined from the lamination parameters V_1^* and V_2^* of the design point.

REFERENCES

- 1 Tsai, S.W. and Hahn, H.T., Introduction to Composite Materials, 1980, Technomic Press
- 2 page 128 of Ref. (1)
- 3 page 79 of Ref. (1)

